

K-MEANS CLUSTERING FOR ANALYZING PRODUCTIVITY IN LIGHT OF R & D SPILLOVER

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ABSTRACT

The differences between countries go far beyond the physical and territorial aspects. Hence, for analytical purposes, it is essential to classify countries in groups based on some of their attributes. Investment in Research and Development (R&D) influences innovations which in turn stimulates growth of a country. In this context the productivity of the R&D expenditure is analysed pragmatically. Present study aims to discover impact of R&D expenditure on its productivity in terms of number of journal articles published, patent applications filed and trademark applications registered. A more significant analysis by means of designing prominent clusters of countries by applying unsupervised learning has been presented. In this division, percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) spending on R&D and its productivity are considered.

KEYWORDS

R&D productivity; data mining; clustering; unsupervised learning

1. INTRODUCTION

R&D productivity is a key indicator of a development of a country. There exists a direct relationship between research and overall development of a nation. Spending on research and development is vital for the advancement in science and technology in addition to social and economic development [9, 12]. Scientific writing in terms of research publication is essential components of academic excellence. Present communication aimed to compare the impact of R&D expenditure on journal articles published, patent applications filed and trademark applications registered.

Igor Prodan has presented a model which depicts dependency of the number of patent applications on R&D expenditure [1]. Research confirms the positive correlation exists between patent applications and R&D expenditure, R&D investment generates patent applications with a delay, which varies from country to country and the quantity of patent applications in developed countries depends more on R&D expenditure in the business sector than on R&D gross domestic expenditure. Meo and Usmani have reported impact of R&D spending on research publications, patents and high technology exports among 47 European countries [2]. This study collected the information regarding per capita GDP, R&D expenditure, number of universities, scientific journals, technology exports and number of patents. The main source for information for this study was Web of Science, World Bank, Thomson Reuters and SCImago/Scopus. This research concluded that, expenditure on R&D, scientific indexed journals and research publications are the most significant contributing factors towards a knowledge economy which in turn give a boost to patent applications, high technology exports and ultimately GDP.

Janodia has compared Research and development spending and patents of India among SAARC and BRICS countries [3]. This study reveals that it is essential to increase in R&D expenditure by the Government of India which encourages research leading to innovation, increasing patenting and larger number of publications. The performance in terms of R&D expenditure and patents is strong among SAARC countries, whereas it is miserable among the countries of BRICS. Yet another paper by Dietmar reported the effect of R&D spillovers on R&D spending and its productivity in German manufacturing firms [4]. The result of panel estimation technique suggested that spillovers affect industries in a heterogeneous manner. High-technology industries spillovers have a increasing productivity effect in adding to encouraging R&D investment.

In the backdrop of the literature portrayed above, the present paper reports clustering of countries based on their R&D expenditure and its productivity. Data Mining promotes distinct tools and algorithms for analyze the data patterns [6]. We have explored efficiency of using machine learning algorithms for designing prominent clusters of countries based on R&D expenditure and its productivity. This paper explains a data mining process for investigating the relationship between the same using WEKA a popular open source free suite [5]. In this process, many criteria, such as R&D expenditure, journal articles, patents and trademark statistics are considered [10, 11]. These datasets have been taken from Knoema a free to use web based public and open data platform. As a broad goal, authors intended in extraction of the hidden knowledge from these datasets and designed clusters of countries based on R&D and its productivity.

2. DATASET DESCRIPTION AND DATA EXPLORATION

The datasets used in the present communication have been taken from Knoema (<http://knoema.com>) a free to use web based public and open data platform launched for the purpose of statistical and infographics analysis. The input dataset containing the numeric values of attributes such as R&D expenditure in terms of percentage of GDP, number of Scientific and technical journal articles, number of Patent applications, number of Trademark applications for 115 countries for the year 2011.

Table 1. Details of R&D attributes

Attribute	Description
R&D expenditure, % of GDP	Current and capital expenditures both public and private on creative work undertaken systematically to increase knowledge and the use of knowledge for new applications. R&D covers basic research, applied research, and experimental development.
Scientific and technical journal articles	The number of scientific and engineering articles published in the following fields: physics, biology, chemistry, mathematics, clinical medicine, biomedical research, engineering and technology, and earth and space sciences.
Patent applications, residents	The number of worldwide patent applications filed through the Patent Cooperation Treaty procedure or with a national patent office.
Trademark applications, direct resident	The number of trademark applications to register a trademark with a national or regional Intellectual Property office.

Thus dataset for the study consists of R&D details of 115 countries representing expenditure and productivity. To preserve the semantics of the clusters, all the values used in this example are real statistics of the countries. Snapshot of dataset shown in figure 1. Table 1 explains details of these attributes and corresponding statistical analysis is given in Table 2. Dataset chosen for the study is analysed through radar diagrams. Figure 2(a-d) gives radar charts of 115 countries for R&D expenditure in terms of percentage of GDP, number of journal articles, number of Patent applications, number of Trademark applications respectively.

	publication	Patent	Trademark	GDP		publication	Patent	Trademark	GDP		publication	Patent	Trademark	GDP
Albania	27	3	274	0.2	Greece	4,534	721	4,065	0.7	Norway	4,777	1,122	3,411	1.7
Algeria	599	94	2,294	0.1	Guatemala	22	4	3854	0.0	Pakistan	1,268	56	14,003	0.3
Argentina	3,863	735	61121	0.6	Hungary	2,289	662	3772	1.2	Panama	67	92	4,167	0.2
Armenia	185	121	1,102	0.3	Iceland	258	50	691	2.6	Paraguay	21	21	569	0.1
Australia	20,603	2,383	40,150	2.4	India	22,481	8841	176386	0.8	Paraguay	9	75	13251	0.1
Austria	5,103	2,154	5,693	2.8	Indonesia	533	533	50,653	0.1	Peru	162	46	15231	0.1
Azerbaijan	149	193	1,915	0.2	Iran, Islamic	8,176	11529	26,825	0.7	Philippines	241	39	10,572	0.1
Bahrain	40	1	269	0.5	Ireland	3,186	567	1,485	1.7	Poland	7,564	186	14,252	0.8
Bangladesh	291	37	6,632	0.2	Israel	6,096	1,360	2,509	4.0	Portugal	4,621	3,879	15,616	1.5
Barbados	16	1	142	0.3	Italy	26,503	8,794	37001	1.3	Qatar	111	571	656	0.5
Belarus	342	1,725	3,649	0.7	Jamaica	51	20	1,119	0.7	Romania	1,626	49	8,389	0.5
Belgium	7,484	636	21,129	2.2	Japan	47,106	287,580	84,671	3.4	Russian Fed	14,151	1,424	33,252	1.1
Bhutan	8	3	8	0.6	Jordan	342	40	2,298	0.4	Senegal	79	26,495	873	0.5
Bolivia	47	52	2321	0.2	Kazakhstan	87	1,415	1,890	0.2	Serbia	1,269	40	1,133	0.8
Bosnia and Herz	54	43	243	0	Kenya	290	135	2,488	1	Seychelles	6	118	67	0.3
Botswana	50	1	329	0.1	Korea, Dem.	4	7,956	769	4	Singapore	4,543	180	4,236	2.2
Brazil	13,148	4,695	122,671	1.2	Korea, Rep.	25,593	138,034	112,576	4.0	Slovak Repu	1,099	1,056	2,332	0.7
Bulgaria	650	262	4058	0.6	Kyrgyz Repu	17	124	180	0.2	Slovenia	1,239	224	2	2.5
Burkina Faso	53	2	34	0.2	Latvia	204	173	1,267	0.7	South Africa	3,125	470	19,522	0.8
Cambodia	33	1	903	0.6	Lebanon	251	102	1,884	0.4	Spain	22,910	656	42,748	1.4
Canada	30115	4,754	21,337	1.8	Lithuania	457	93	2,756	0.9	Sri Lanka	130	3,430	200	0.2
Chile	1,979	339	25,254	0.4	Luxembourg	85	85	5,814	1.4	Sweden	9,473	194	9,290	3.4
China	89,894	415,829	1,273,827	1.8	Macao SAR	4	4	476	0.0	Switzerland	10,019	2,004	432	2.2
Colombia	727	183	16,976	0.2	Macedonia	77	37	917	0.2	Tajikistan	18	1,597	161	0.1
Costa Rica	106	14	6,759	0.5	Madagascar	33	3	621	0.1	Tanzania	121	4	98	0.5
Croatia	1,289	230	1461	0.8	Malaysia	2,092	1,076	13001	1.1	Thailand	2,304	121	23,457	0.3
Cuba	224	62	256	0.3	Malta	46	8	423	0.7	The Gambia	3	927	105	0.1
Cyprus	211	4	646	0.5	Mexico	4128	1,065	71,091	0.4	Tunisia	1,016	47	1,675	1.1
Czech Repub	4127	783	8091	1.6	Moldova	76	97	1300	0.4	Turkey	8,328	137	103748	0.9
Denmark	6,071	1574	3060	3.0	Monaco	20	6	388	0	Uganda	158	3,885	563	0.6
Ecuador	60	4	8851	0.2	Mongolia	25	110	2542	0.3	Ukraine	1,727	6	16,836	0.7
Egypt, Arab	2,515	618	439	0.4	Montenegro	28	20	94	0.4	United Arab	324	2,649	3,208	0.5
Estonia	514	62	888	2.4	Morocco	386	169	5490	0.7	United Kingd	46,035	26	31,253	1.8
Ethiopia	170	1	42	0.2	Myanmar	9	42	4007	0.1	United State	208610	15,343	256,775	2.8
Finland	4,878	1650	5,403	3.8	Nepal	64	6	2,204	0.3	Uruguay	290	247,750	2,458	0.4
France	31,686	14,655	85,713	2.2	Netherlands	15,508	2,585	1023	2.0	Venezuela	302	20	11,066	0.4
Georgia	118	138	841	0.2	New Zealand	3,472	1,501	8,632	1.3	Vietnam	432	282	22,376	0.5
Germany	46,259	46,986	60,606	2.9	Nigeria	439	64	20,560	1	Yemen Rep.	33	300	2,191	0.6

Figure 1. Snapshot of dataset

Table 2. Statistical Analysis of R&D attributes

	R&D expenditure, % of GDP	Journal Articles	Patent Applications	Trademark Applications
Minimum	0	3	1	2
Maximum	4	208610	415829	1273827
Mean	0.957	7016.791	11236.261	27336.983
Standard Deviation	0.999	22657.798	53425.323	122676.98

Figure 2(a). Radar chart for countries' R&D expenditure in terms of percentage of GDP

Figure 2(b). Radar chart for countries' number of Scientific and technical journal articles

Figure 2(c). Radar chart for countries' number of Patent applications, residents

Figure 2(d). Radar chart for countries' number of Trademark applications, direct resident

3. K-MEANS CLUSTERING: THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

K-Means is a simple unsupervised learning algorithm for cluster design and analysis. The aim of this algorithm is to find the best split of N entities into K groups, so that the total distance between the members of group and its corresponding centroid, representative of the group, is minimized. Thus the goal is to partition the N entities into K sets S_i , $i=1, 2, \dots, K$ in order to minimize the sum of squares error within cluster [7]. This error is defined as:

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{p \in C_i} |p - m_i|^2 \quad (1)$$

Where E is the sum of the square error for all points in the data set; p is the point in data space representing a given object; and the mean of cluster S_i is m_i . In other words, for each data item in each cluster, the distance from the event to its cluster center is squared, and the distances are summed.

In this technique, clusters are dependent on the choice of the initial cluster centroids. Randomly K data items are selected as initial cluster centers followed by the distances of all points are calculated by Euclidean distance formula. Data items having less distance to centroids are moved to the appropriate cluster. This process is continued until no more alterations occur in clusters. The Figure 3 shows basic K-mean clustering algorithm [7].

Figure 3. K-means Clustering Algorithm

4. CLUSTER DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

In regard to the scenario mentioned in the introduction, to analyze countries similarity and assign them to the clusters, the R&D attributes taken into account. The k-means algorithm is a technique for grouping entities according to the similarity of their attributes [6]. As the presenting problem consists of dividing countries into similar groups, it is plausible that K-means can be applied to this task. As observed in Figure 4 three clusters are created to classify datasets into three categories.

The implementation of K-means generated three clusters, consisting of 9, 83 and 23 countries. Corresponding details are tabulated in Table 3. Figure 5 gives scatter chart of cluster density generated in Weka. Analyzing the cluster means, we can relate each group with each of the three classes of countries:

- Cluster 0 formed by countries has highest R&D expenditure, Patent applications and Trademark applications and medium in Journal Publications
- Cluster 1 formed by countries has lowest R & D expenditure as well as lowest in Journal Publications and Trademark Applications. But they have medium number of Patents
- Cluster 2 formed by other countries has medium R & D expenditure as well as medium in Trademark Applications. These countries have highest Journal Publications and lowest in Patents

Figure 4. Clustering Results in Weka

Table 3. Clusters of countries

Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2
China	Albania	Macao SAR,
Finland	Algeria	Macedonia,
Germany	Argentina	FYR
Israel	Armenia	Madagascar
Japan	Azerbaijan	Malaysia
Korea, Dem. Rep	Bahrain	Malta
Korea, Rep.	Bangladesh	Mexico
Sweden	Barbados	Moldova
United States	Belarus	Monaco
	Bhutan	Mongolia
	Bolivia	Montenegro
	Bosnia and	Morocco
	Herzegovina	Myanmar
	Botswana	Nepal
	Bulgaria	Nigeria
	Burkina Faso	Pakistan
	Cambodia	Panama
	Chile	Paraguay
	Colombia	Paraguay
	Costa Rica	Peru
	Croatia	Philippines
	Cuba	Poland
	Cyprus	Qatar
	Ecuador	Romania
	Egypt, Arab Rep.	Russian
	Ethiopia	Federation
	Georgia	Senegal
	Greece	Serbia
	Guatemala	Seychelles
	India	Slovak
	Indonesia	Republic
	Iran, Islamic Rep.	South Africa
	Jamaica	Sri Lanka
	Jordan	Tajikistan
	Kazakhstan	Tanzania
	Kenya	Thailand
	Kyrgyz Republic	The Gambia
	Latvia	Tunisia
	Lebanon	Turkey
	Lithuania	Uganda
		Ukraine
		United Arab
		Emirates
		Venezuela
		Vietnam
		Yemen Rep.
		Zambia
		Australia
		Austria
		Belgium
		Brazil
		Canada
		Czech Republic
		Denmark
		Estonia
		France
		Hungary
		Iceland
		Ireland
		Italy
		Luxembourg
		Netherlands
		New Zealand
		Norway
		Portugal
		Singapore
		Slovenia
		Spain
		Switzerland
		United
		Kingdom

Figure 5. Cluster density

3. CONCLUSIONS

Our investigation using the K-means clustering algorithm in fact one of its kinds systematic modus operandi for perceiving the performance metrics for the benefit of the policy makers, scientific community and the society at large. This study has analyzed the number of research publications, patent applications and trademarks registered with reference to percentage of GDP spending on R&D. Unsupervised learning algorithm used for designing three clusters of countries based on these dataset. Countries belonging to cluster-0 should focus on increasing number of journal publications. Cluster 1 formed by countries must re-plan their R&D funds to motivate researchers in increasing research productivity.

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